

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF TRANSPLANTED OF ONION CULTIVATION IN AKOLA DISTRICT

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Abstract

The present study was undertaken in Akola district of Vidarbha region. The onion was selected for the present study. Two tehsils from Akola district were selected for the present study. From each tehsil two villages were selected. Total 60 farmers were selected. The scheduled was designed for primary data collection keeping in view the objectives of the study. The data pertains for the year 2023-24. To accomplish the objectives, of the present study simple tabular analysis was used. The economics of onion production was calculated by using standard cost concept. In transplanted onion cultivation nuclear family concept was predominantly observed. The average family size of transplanted method of cultivators was less than 5 members. In transplanted method of cultivation 1.67 per cent of farmers are illiterate and rest of them are educated. The cropping intensity was worked out to 168.30 per cent in rabi season highest area was sown under chickpea crop i.e. 19.50 per cent followed by onion crop i.e. 16.59 per cent. In Transplanting method of onion cultivation Cost "A" Rs. 119179.85/- i.e. 60.99 per cent of the total cost. The cost B was worked out to be Rs. 123536.28/-. The per hectare cost of cultivation of onion was Rs.195416.01/-. The per quintal cost of production was Rs. 808.91/-. The highest input output ratio at cost 'C' was recorded in broadcasting method of cultivation i.e. 1:1.89.

Keywords: Economic analysis, Transplanted, standard cost concept, onion production

Introduction

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is one of the important condiments used in all households all round the year. It belongs to the family Aliaceae. Its primary centre of origin is central Asia and Mediterranean may be a secondary centre of Origin. It is commonly known as "Queen of Kitchen" due to its highly valued flavour, aroma and unique taste. Among the bulb crops, onion is that the most important vegetable crop grown since ancient times in the country. Onion crop plays a pivotal role within the human diet. The onion is rich in B-complex vitamin.

India is largest producer in the world with area of 16.28 million hectares (doca.gov.in) followed by China in 2022 as per FAO data. India (31687000 MT) is largest producer in the world with share of 25% followed by China (24542011 MT) in 2022 as per FAO data (agriexchange.apeda.gov.in). Production in 2022-23 (Final Estimates) is estimated to be 302.08 Lakh Tonne compared to 316.87 Lakh Tonne in 2021-22. (pib.gov.in). Onion is the second most important commercial crops of the India which is next to Potato. The Major Onion producing states are Maharashtra, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Gujarat, Bihar, Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan, Haryana and Telangana. Maharashtra ranks first in Onion production with a share of 35% followed by Madhya Pradesh with a share of 17 % in 2023-24 (2nd Advance Estimate).(apeda.gov.in). There is a lot of demand for Indian Onion in the world. The country has exported 1,717,439.35 MT of fresh onion to the world, worth Rs. 3,922.78 crores/ 473.72 USD Millions during the year 2023-24.

In the Vidarbha region of Maharashtra, the districts where onions are grown include Akola, Wardha, Amaravati, Bhandara, Buldhana, Chandrapur, Nagpur, and Yavatmal. Onions are mainly grown as a second crop after the Kharif crop and are sown from November to January. They are ready to harvest during April to May.

In the Vidarbha region, the cultivation of onions is on the rise. It is increasingly popular as a commercial cash crop in the Akola district. According to the District Superintendent Agricultural Office in Akola, the area, production, and productivity of onions in the district were approximately 8000 hectares, 1789 metric tonnes, and 223.68 quintals per hectare respectively in the year 2021-22.

Importance of study

The study analysed the cost and returns per hectare of transplanted onion cultivation. This analysis is crucial because onions are commercially important for growers in Akola district. The study focused on examining the current utilization level of various inputs such as labour, irrigation, and fertilizers. It emphasized the commercial importance of onions as a vegetable crop in the specific region, suggesting that onions are grown over a large area in the district and are considered a profitable crop.

Therefore, this study was planned with the following**Objective**

1. To study the socio-economic characteristics of onion growers
2. To study the economics of transplanted onion production

Methodology

The present study was conducted in Akola district of the Vidarbha region, focusing on onion cultivation. Two tehsils from Akola district were included in the study, with two villages selected from each tehsil, totalling 60 participating farmers. The data collection schedule was designed to align with the study's objectives and pertains to the year 2023-24. A simple tabular analysis was used to achieve the study's objectives, and the economics of onion production was calculated using the standard cost concept.

Cost-A

- a) Hired human labour
- b) Total bullock labour
- c) Total machinery labour
- d) Seed
- e) Plant Protection
- f) Manure
- g) Fertilizer (N, P, K & S)
- h) Irrigation charges
- i) Depreciation on implements, machinery and farm. buildings.
- j) Land revenue and other taxes.
- k) Interest on working capital
- i) Miscellaneous expenses (Artisans etc.)

Cost-B

It comprises of Cost-A plus rental value of owned land and interest on owned fixed capital (excluding land).

Cost-C

It includes Cost-B plus imputed value of family labour. The economics of production of transplanted onion were estimated as gross returns, net returns and benefit cost ratio.

Gross Returns

Returns obtained from the sale of crops output i.e. Main Produce and by-produce.

Net Returns

Net returns were computed at different cost concept i.e. Cost A. Cost B. and Cost C by deducting respective cost from the gross returns.

Output-Input Ratio

The output-input ratio were worked out with reference to cost "A cost 'B' and cost "C".

Output-input ratio at Cost A = Gross income / Cost A

Output-input ratio at Cost B = Gross income / Cost B

Output-input ratio at Cost C = Gross income / Cost C

Results and Discussions.**Table No. 1 Distribution of farmers according to size of holding**

Sr. No.	Size of holding	Method of cultivation
		Transplanted
1	Small (up to 2 Ha)	20 (33.34)
2	Medium (2.01 to 4.00)	28 (46.66)
3	Large (4.01 and above)	12 (20.00)
4	Total	60 (100.00)

(Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentages to total)

It could be seen in table 1 that, the total 60 farmers were selected for present study, there was large no of medium farmers i.e. 28 while small and large farmers are 20 and 12 respectively.

Table No. 2 Distribution of farmers according to age (No.)

Sr. No.	Age (Years)	Farmer selected
		Transplanted
1	Young (<35)	17 (28.33)
2	Middle age (35 – 50)	28 (46.67)
3	Older (>50)	15 (25.00)
4	Total	60 (100.00)

(Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentages to total)

The data in Table 2 indicates in large no of farmers falls in middle age group i.e. 35-50 years age. There are large no of famers in young category i.e. less than 35 years as compared to older farmers.

Table No: 3 Educational pattern of selected farmers (No.)

Sr. No	Particulars	Transplanted Cultivars
1	Illiterate	1 (1.67)
2	Primary	3 (5.00)
3	secondary school	13 (21.66)
4	Higher secondary	30 (50.00)
5	Graduate & above	13 (21.67)
6	Total	60 (100.00)

(Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentages to total)

The data in Table 3 indicates that there are very less percentage of Illiteracy was observed in transplanted group i.e. 1.67 per cent. Large no of farmers completed there higher secondary education i.e. 30. There are 13 farmers who completed graduation.

Table No: 4 Average family size of selected farmers (No.)

Sr. no.	Size of family (Member)	Transplanted
1	<5	35 (58.33)
2	5-9	21 (35.00)
3	>9	4 (6.67)
	Total	60 (100.00)

(Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentages to total)

Information presented in Table 4 revealed that the family with less than 5 members are highest 58.33 per cent. There are about 35.00 per cent family with 5-9 members and 6.67 per cent with more than 9 members.

Table No: 5 Family type of selected farmers according to different size group (No.)

Sr. No.	Family size	Transplanted
1	joint	6 (10.00)

2	Nuclear	54 (90.00)
	Total	60 (100.00)

(Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentages to total)

Table No. 6 Distribution of onion farmers according to their farming experience (No.)

Onion Farming Experience	Number of Farmers	Percentage
Up to 10 years	21	17.50
11-20 Years	53	44.17
21-30 Years	26	21.66
above 30	20	16.67
Total	120	100.00

Table 6 shows that the farmers having farming experience of up to 10 years were 17.50 per cent, 11- 20 years were 44.17 per cent, 21-30 years were 21.66 per cent while 16.67 per cent farmers had experience more than 30 years.

Table: 5.7 Land utilization pattern of selected cultivators

(Area in ha)

Sr.No	Particulars	Size group
		Transplanted
1	Total land holding	2.85 (100.00)
2	Fallow land	0.02 (0.70)
3	Net cultivated area	2.83 (99.30)
4	Area sown more than once	1.90 (66.67)
5	Gross cropped area	4.73
6	Cropping intensity (%)	167.13

(Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentages to total land holding)

It is observed from Table 7 that, the total land holding of transplanted cultivators was 2.85 ha. The proportion of net cultivable area to total land holding in respect to transplanted group was 99.30 per cent. The percentage of current fallows to total land was 0.70 per cent. The percentage of area sown more than once to total land was worked out 66.67 per cent. The cropping intensity was worked out 167.13 per cent.

Table: 5.8 Cropping pattern of selected cultivators

Sr. No	Particulars	Size group
		Transplanted
A	Kharif	
1	Soybean	1.96 (41.44)
2	Tur	0.30 (6.34)
3	Cotton	0.41 (8.67)
4	Fodder	0.10 (2.11)
	Total of Kharif crop	2.77 (58.56)
B	Rabi	
1	Onion	0.73 (15.43)
2	Wheat	0.14 (2.96)
3	Chickpea	0.99 (20.93)
4	Jowar	0.05 (1.06)
	Total of Rabi crop	1.90 (40.17)
C	Perennial crops	
1	Lemon	0.06 (1.27)
	Total of Perennial crop	0.06 (1.27)
D	Gross Cropped area	4.73 (100.00)

(Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentages to total grossed crop area)

It can be seen from Table 8 that, highest area was sown under soybean crop (41.44 per cent) followed by chickpea (20.93 per cent), onion (15.43 per cent), cotton (8.67 per cent), tur (6.34 per cent) and wheat (2.96), Lemon (1.27), fodder (2.11) per cent respectively.

In Kharif season, the area allocated under Kharif crops was 58.56 per cent of the gross cropped area. In kharif season the cropping pattern was dominated by soybean crop i.e. 41.44 per cent.

In Rabi season area allocated, onion and chickpea were the important crops grown by the selected farmers. It was observed that, the area under onion was 15.43 per cent and that of chickpea was 20.93 per cent of the gross cropped area. In very small proportion area were used for cultivation of wheat crop.

Table No: 9 Cost of cultivation of transplanted onion

							(Rs/ha)	
Sr. No.	Item	Unit		Input/ ha.	Cost/ Unit of input	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₂ '	
1	2	3			4	5	6	
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	84.92	327.35	27798.955	14.23	
		Female	Days	147.61	259.92	38366.652	19.63	
		Total	Days	232.53		66165.607	33.86	
2	Bullock Labour		Days	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
3	Machine charges	Hired	Hrs	5.35	946.41	5063.27	2.59	
4	Seed		kgs	8.13	944.75	7682.2467	3.93	
5	Manure		Qtls.	10.11	272.96	2759.6547	1.41	
6	Fertilizer	N kg/h	Kg.	86.55	44.44	3846.67	1.97	
		P kg/h	Kg.	100.23	45.53	4563.57	2.34	
		K kg/h	Kg.	65.99	45.54	3005.15	1.54	
		S Kg/h	Kg.	30.33	44.71	1356.12	0.69	
		Total	Kg.	283.1		12771.521	6.54	
7	Irrigation charges.	(Rs.)				6204.2708	3.17	
8	Incidental charges	(Rs.)				1013.4	0.52	
9	Plant Protection	(Rs.)				7321.15	3.75	
10	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)				1087	0.56	
11	Working Cap.	(Rs.)				114556.77	58.62	
12	Intrest on working Cap.	(Rs.)				2672.99	1.37	
13	Depreciation	(Rs.)				3643.333	1.86	
14	Land Revenue	(Rs.)				76.10	0.04	
15	COST "A1"	(Rs.)				119179.85	60.99	
16	Rent paid for Leased in land					0.00	0.00	
17	COST "A2"					119179.85	60.99	
18	Fixed capital					43564.257	22.29	
19	Int. on Fix.Cap. @ 10%					4356.4257	2.23	
20	COST "B1"					123536.28	63.22	
21	Rental Value of Land	(Rs.)				61470.831	31.46	
22	COST "B2"					185007.11	94.67	
23	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	18.67	313.01	5843.93	2.99	
		Female	Days	17.92	254.74	4564.97	2.34	
		Total	Days	36.60		10408.9	5.33	
24	Cost " C1 "	(Rs.)				133945.18	68.54	
25	Cost " C2 "	(Rs.)				195416.01	100.00	
26	10% Cost C2*					19541.601		
27	Cost " C3 "					214957.61		
28	Yield per hectare	(qt)		241.58	1528.61	369281.58		
29	Value of By-produce/ha.	(qt)						
30	Value of total produce	Rs.		241.58	1528.61	369281.58		
31	Per quintal cost of Prod.	(Rs.)				808.91		

Table 9 revealed that per hectare cost of cultivation of transplanted onion for Rs. 195416.01/-. The major item was working capital i.e 58.62 per cent followed by, hired human labour 33.86 per cent, rental value of land 31.46 per cent, fixed capital 22.29 per cent, fertilizer cost 6.54 per cent, plant protection 3.75 per cent share to cost C₂

respectively. The per cent share of Cost A₂ and Cost B₂ were 60.99 per cent and 94.67 per cent respectively in total cost. The per ha yield was 241.58 quintal and value of total produce was Rs. 369281.58/-. The per quintal cost of production was Rs. 808.91/-

Table No: 10 Cost and returns from broadcasted and transplanted onion. (Rs/qt.)

Sr No.	Particulars	Transplanted
1	Yield (qtl.)	241.58
2	Value Main Produce	369281.5766
	By Produce	-

3	Total Produce	369281.5766
4	Total Cost	
	cost A1	119179.8498
	cost A2	119179.8498
	cost B1	123536.28
	cost B2	185007.1066
	cost C1	133945.1806
	cost C2	195416.0116
	cost C3	214957.6128
5	Net Return Over	
	cost A1	250101.7267
	cost A2	250101.7267
	cost B1	245745.301
	cost B2	184274.47
	cost C1	235336.396
	cost C2	173865.5649
	cost C3	154323.9638
6	Input Output ratio at	
	cost A1	3.10
	cost A2	3.10
	cost B1	2.99
	cost B2	2.00
	cost C1	2.76
	cost C2	1.89
	cost C3	1.72

It is revealed from the Table 10 that, The onion yield realized by transplanting method was 241.58 quintals per hectare. The per hectare gross returns realized for transplanted onion growers were Rs. 369281.58/-. The net returns (returns over Cost C) was Rs. 173865.56/- for transplanted method. The highest input output ratio at cost 'C₂' was recorded for transplanted growers i.e. 1:1.89.

The input output ratio which is an indicator of economic efficiency in crop production for the crop and other discussion indicated that transplanted onion cultivation registered a good input output ratio 1:1.89 means this is profitable method of cultivation.

Conclusions

In transplanted method of onion cultivation medium size of holding is predominantly observed.

Among selected growers large number of growers are middle age farmers.

There are large no of families with members less than 5 followed by 5 to 9 members and more than 9 members.

In transplanted method of cultivation only 1.67 per cent farmers are illiterate rest of them are educated.

In type of family nuclear family type was predominantly observed.

The cropping intensity was worked out to 167.13 per cent.

In rabi season highest area sown under chickpea crop followed by onion i.e. 15.43 per cent.

Transplanted method of onion cultivation Cost "A" Rs. 119179.85 i.e. 60.99 per cent of the total cost. The cost B was worked out to be Rs. 123536.28/-. The per hectare cost of cultivation of onion was Rs. 195416.01/-. The per quintal cost of production was Rs. 808.91/-.

The highest input output ratio at cost "C" was recorded in transplanted method of onion cultivation i.e. 1:1.89.

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